

D6.6 Demo videos

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Executive summary

This deliverable presents the definition and steps made towards the development of a set of demonstrative videos presenting and guiding wine makers through the different smart services developed and deployed into the VitiGEOSS Platform. The platform offers integrated services for sub-seasonal and seasonal predictions, crop management, disease warning, business operations and sustainability monitoring. The videos have been designed following a common design format to ensure consistency between them.

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List of abbreviations

<i>EU</i>	<i>European Union</i>
<i>EO</i>	<i>Earth Observation</i>
<i>WP</i>	<i>Work Package</i>
<i>VCI</i>	<i>Visual Corporative Image</i>

Introduction

VitiGEOSS is a 3.5-year project aiming to promote the use of European open Earth observation (EO) services, developing an **innovative vineyard management tool based on the integration of EO and in-field sensors** to increase the resolution and reliability of satellite information applied in the viticulture sector.

The project also has the objective to respond to future challenges of the worldwide food and wine industry, which requires the **intensification of the production in a sustainable way, mitigating the effects of climate change, reducing negative environmental externalities and promoting local economic growth.**

Eurecat is the partner leader of the **SubTask 6.2.3. Demo video (M20-M36)**. The purpose of this subtask is to develop a video that will guide users through the different smart services developed in WP2 and the portal deployed by WP3, while providing the context to understand the project challenges, motivations, and outcomes. Partners agreed to not only produce one video showing the whole platform, but a total of five demo videos, one for each of the five intelligent services, including:

- **Weather & climate forecasts**
- **Phenological monitoring**
- **Crop status**
- **Disease management**
- **Business & sustainability management**

This deliverable summarises the structure, content and elements of the demo videos developed in the scope of SubTask 6.2.3. The document includes the script prepared, design elements considered for deploying the VitiGEOSS project brand and access to the video uploaded to the project's YouTube channel.

Demo videos developed

Eurecat, with the contribution of BSC, ELEAF and LINKS, has produced five demo videos presenting each informative service included in the VitiGEOSS platform. The services integrate and improve existing solutions that couple satellite imagery with in-field sensors to optimise vineyard management and improve the agriculture business operations at an economic, environmental, and local level.

The goal of the demo videos is two-fold:

- Guide end-users through each service functionalities and train them on how to use it.
- Disseminate the VitiGEOSS platform amongst wine makers to raise awareness of the project final goal.

More information about each of the demo videos is provided below.

Demo video #1: Weather & Climate

1. This service relies on advanced techniques to provide sub-seasonal (for the next weeks, up to 1 month) to seasonal climate forecasts (for the next months) in combination with short-term weather forecasts (up to 10 days ahead). These forecasts aim to help farmers prepare in advance for unusual climate conditions and extreme events that can damage their crop.

1.1 Script

- Click on 'Analyse' and select 'Weather & Climate' Service in the top middle menu. In the menu on the right, select the vineyard and parcel.
- The short-term forecast services will automatically load the air temperature forecast. After some seconds, a multipanel graphic will display the 3-hourly forecast for the following two days and a half. The variable and its units will be shown on the vertical axis on the left.
- The green bottom indicating the variable name is used to select a different variable.
- Click on 'Short term' and select the 'Subseasonal' climate forecast. For each week, at least 3 percentages will appear, and by moving the pointer on each bar, a label will indicate a range of values for the selected variable.
- For instance, for the week from 11 to 17 of June, the probability of the temperatures being below 23°C is 0%, there is a probability of 21% that the temperatures are in the normal conditions for that week of the year, and a 79% of probability of being greater than 26°C.
- By selecting, the 'Seasonal' climate forecast, a similar bar plot will appear, showing the forecast for the next 3 months.
- In case the forecast for a specific place and time of the year has not proven to perform well enough in the past, the label 'Uncertain' will be shown on top of the bars, meaning that it is better to use the mean past observations as future prediction rather than the seasonal forecasts for this particular location and period of the year.

1.2 Demo video produced

The demo video on the weather & climate forecast services can be found here: <https://youtu.be/N4NDf8C65Mg>

Figure 1: Screenshots of the demo video on the weather & climate forecast service

2. Demo video #2: Phenological monitoring

The phenological monitoring service integrated in the VitiGEASS platform is an automated system used to predict and monitor the whole phenological annual cycle through the synergic use of phenological models, satellite and in-field observations, allowing users to better plan and organise the whole vineyard management and optimise resources.

2.1 Script

- From the main dashboard, you can choose among its own vineyards. Selecting a vineyard, the map will be centered on the management units. By clicking on it, all the information is displayed.
- The 'Phenology' section shows the outcomes of the phenology service. This service performs the monitoring (detection) and the forecast (prediction) of the phenological phases of the vineyard according to the Baggioini scale.
- For this management unit, the outcomes of 4 different models are shown. Each of them works with different data sources:
 - 1) Satellites for Deep EO3, 2) weather station for Deep Weather Obs, 3) weather station + weather forecast for the Mechanistic, and 4) Deep Weather forecast models.
- The presence of diverse models ensures the scalability of the service, because it can work in different settings according to the data sources available.

- It is also possible to insert the achieved phenology date for each phase to keep track of them and have an assessment on the accuracy of the results given by the service.
- Here, you can compare the outcome of the models across various management units through the dedicated section “Phenology”.

2.2 Demo video produced

The demo video on the phenological monitoring service can be found here: <https://youtu.be/QL-F9inUmwv>

Phase	Deep weather obs (detection)	Deep weather forecast (prediction)	Deep ECI (detection)	Mechanistic (prediction)	Actual month	Actual day	Save
Bud Break	9 Apr (week 15)	9 Apr (week 15)	27 Mar (week 13)	13 Apr (week 16)	April	15	
Blooming	23 May (week 21)	23 May (week 21)	29 May (week 22)	31 May (week 22)	Month	Day	
Fruit Set	3 Jun (week 23)	3 Jun (week 23)	5 Jun (week 23)	15 Jun (week 25)	Month	Day	
Veraison					Month	Day	
Ripening					Month	Day	
Leaf Fall					Month	Day	

The section phenology shows the outcomes of the phenology service

It is also possible insert the achieved phenology date for each phase, in order to keep track of them and have an assessment on the accuracy of the results given by the service

It is also possible insert the achieved phenology date for each phase, in order to keep track of them and have an assessment on the accuracy of the results given by the service

Figure 2: Screenshots of the phenological monitoring demo video

3.

Demo video #3: Crop status

This service uses satellite imagery to monitor key indicators describing vegetation health status, crop productivity, crop water consumption and crop nitrogen content in order to optimise irrigation, sampling or selective harvesting, leading to better grape quality and production.

3.1 Script

- After logging in, you land on the home page. On this page, an overview of all the fields linked to the area selected is shown. A window is located on the left of the screen, and provides an overview of all fields in the account.
- By clicking on the green button, you can select the parameter to visualise.
- In the top right, you can select another area and move there.
- Different filters can be applied through the menu. After adjusting the filter, click on the green PLAY button to apply it. The fields that comply with the filter will appear in the lower half of the tab.

- When clicking on a field in the overview mode, the field details are shown. These details include the crop, sowing date and data values for the week selected in the mid-top-bar.
- When double clicking on the field or selecting “Analysis” - “Single Field” in the top bar, you can access the data page for that field.
- All data parameters are visualized in a graph. When clicking on a parameter, it becomes the only one visible. You can select the set of parameters you are interested in viewing.
- By scrolling down, you can find the spatial overview maps for this field per week per parameter. If you click on a map, it pops up in a separate screen.
- When pressing the “Single Field” button, you can select “graph” in the drop-down menu. This graph visualizes all selected fields in the passport. The fields can be selected by pressing on the field name underneath the graph.

3.2 Demo video produced

The demo video on the crop status service can be found here: <https://youtu.be/xtvyeNuzOQ4>

Figure 3: Screenshots of the crop status service demo video

Demo video #4: Disease management

The disease management service allows to forecast the disease evolution, considering the meteorological conditions and crop status to optimise the number of treatments and resources used to assure its effectivity.

4. 4.1 Script

- Once on the home page, you should click on the "Map" menu. From here, the user will be able to access two drop-down menus on the upper right part of the screen.
- The first menu allows to choose between the different vineyards of accompany (each user will only be able to see their own data), while the second menu allows access to the plot of interest.
- After the map is loaded, the user will be able to see the different plots registered on the platform. A specific plot can be selected by clicking on it with the mouse.
- Then, a pop-up window will appear listing the different services that can be selected. Among them, you will find "Disease management".
- A drop-down menu will appear again. This allows to select the time frame of the disease predictions.
- Once the desired horizon has been chosen, in this case short-term predictions, we can see the risk and recommended treatment for downy mildew and powdery mildew.
- At the bottom, the results of the previous predictions made to date are presented in a very intuitive way, with their corresponding risk level and treatment.
- Another functionality available is setting a risk threshold, which allows to receive notifications. This can be set up through the toolbar, by clicking on "analyse" and then "disease alerts".
- Here, you will be able to set a threshold level for each plot, time frame and microorganism to receive notifications.

4.2 Demo video produced

The demo video on the disease management service can be found here: <https://youtu.be/q1AMWKHQYNO>

VITIGE OSS PLATFORM INTELLIGENT SERVICES FOR VINEYARD MANAGEMENT

Disease management

Forecasting the disease evolution to optimise the treatments and resources used

Once landing on the home page, the user should go to the "map" menu. From here the user will be able to see that there are two drop-down menus on the upper right part of the screen

A drop menu will appear again. This will allow the user to select the time frame of the disease predictions

Here the user will be able to set a threshold level for each plot, time frame and microorganism to receive notifications

Figure 4: Screenshots of the disease management service demo video

5. Demo video #5: Business & Sustainability manager

This service consists of a resource optimiser and planner service that allows better timing of field operations and better planning of resources needed, thus reducing the use of raw materials, and promoting more sustainable winegrowing.

5.1 Script

- Starting from the home page you can access the “Business” smart service in the drop-down menu that can be opened by hovering over the “Analyse” button on the top left corner.
- Once there, you can see a calendar-based visualization of the field tasks that must be performed and to which working groups they are assigned to.
- As you can see, the tasks and their time duration are marked in specific team colors, indicating which teams are responsible for that task. The days appearing in grey represent treatment days in which the workers cannot access the fields.
- You can scroll up and down to see all the parcels, as well as forward and backward in time to see the whole schedule.
- You can access the schedule of the external companies by clicking on the “external companies” window.

- To generate a new schedule, you must access the configuration button, which opens a window where you can view the current scenario and modify the parameters.
- Once the configuration is updated and saved, you can click on “start” to obtain a new schedule. The “stop” button can be used to stop this process at any moment.
- To access the sustainability KPIs you must return to the home menu and access a parcel by selecting it on the top right drop-down menu.
- Once on the parcel, you can see a display of the sustainability KPIs by selecting the parcel and accessing the “sustainability” window on the informative panel that pops up.

5.2 Demo video produced

The demo video on the business & sustainability manager service can be found here: <https://youtu.be/CRrou6WD9V0>

VITIGE OSS PLATFORM INTELLIGENT SERVICES FOR VINEYARD MANAGEMENT

Business and sustainability management

Resource optimiser and planner service to improve the timing of fields operations

Once the configuration is updated and saved, you can click on “start” to obtain a new schedule, the stop button can be used to stop this process at any moment

Starting from the home page, you can access the “Business” smart service in the drop-down menu opened by hovering over the “Analyze” button on the top left corner

Once on the parcel you can see a display of the sustainability KPIs by selecting the parcel and accessing the “sustainability” window on the informative panel that pops up

Figure 5: Screenshots of the business & sustainability manager demo video

Structure and design elements

For the development of the VitiGEOSS services demo videos, a common format was defined regarding the structure and design elements used. Firstly, an animation of the logo of the project was designed in Adobe After Effects to be used as the entry slide of all videos. On the other hand, a final slide animated with VitiGEOSS key information was produced, including: a) VitiGEOSS website, b) VitiGEOSS social media accounts, c) partners logos, d) reference to EU funding.

Figure 6: Entry and end animated slide used in project's demo videos

All videos follow the same structure, consisting of a recording of the VitiGEOSS platform, accompanied with an explanatory text that appears at the bottom of the screen.

Figure 7: View of the purple rectangle used to allocate the script guiding the user through the platform

Music was used as a key element in the videos, to give them rhythm and dynamism. The soundtrack used is copyright-free, selected from YouTube Music Studio.

Conclusions

The VitiGEOSS platform is still under development and testing under WP2 and WP3. Therefore, the platform will be updated, and the look of services will most probably change to be optimized according to end-users' feedback in the next months.

A second batch of demo videos will be produced at a later stage, including testimonials of users about project results. The demo videos produced will be compiled in D6.11 - Demo video - second version (M40), which will be produced by EUT.